

PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN THE CONCEPT OF MODERN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In modern conditions, the main goal of education is to educate a person capable of self-education and self-development in order to freely and harmoniously determine their own destiny in society, culture and profession. This article focuses on the organization of the educational process on the basis of pedagogical-psychological approaches in the concept of modern education.

Developing education prioritizes the creation of conditions that enhance the creative potential of students in all areas of personality (emotional, personal, spiritual and moral). Practice-oriented teaching is increasingly used in education, whose task is to develop students' ability to develop knowledge through thinking based on their own experience. For a psychologist working in the field of education, "Does education create the conditions for a child's full development, mental and physical health, and personal growth?" It is very important to answer the question. Any action of the pedagogical community is in accordance with the Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted by the United Nations in 1989 and ratified in Russia in 1990.

As a constructive, practice-oriented science of educational psychology, it has enormous potential to play an important

role in the development of each of its subjects - children, parents and teachers. Modern pedagogical psychology is based on the principle of continuity of subject and object. It makes the construction of life the starting point of research, which in turn views research as an event design, thereby shaping the minds of psychologists and educators. The psychological and pedagogical theories presented in the textbook interpret the information gathered, make complex events understandable, predict the consequences of decisions, and discover new evidence. But most importantly, they solve one of the most important problems, what should be the psychologist working in this training, what principles should determine his professional and personal position. And this largely depends on the knowledge of the psychologist, which can be obtained from

textbooks. But, in many ways, a psychologist's effectiveness is determined by his or her personal characteristics: deep interest in people, emotional stability, respect for the other person's rights, understanding of professional duty, ability to inspire confidence, and a high level of self-awareness. The code of ethics of the psychologist in Russia has not become a regulator of his professional activity. Most importantly, it is a responsibility imposed on him, to be aware of every action, to understand the consequences of the decisions made.

The basic and universal principles of the work of a psychologist in education areas follows.

- Humanism - respect for the identity and rights of the subjects of the educational process, the recognition of their growth as a person as a priority and the main goal of the psychologist;

- harmful attitude to the environment - rejection of any form of expansion, focus on manipulative, non-violent methods of work, ensuring a safe environment;

- Democracy - reliance on democratic principles in the implementation of educational work; the psychologist strives to take a position of equal cooperation, partnership and partnership with parents, children and teachers;

- constructive - the work of the psychologist is not to identify errors, irregularities, but to find sources for the development and improvement of the learning process;

- openness - the psychologist's actions are carried out in an open, transparent manner;

- comprehensibility and acceptability of the methods used by the psychologist for educators;

- Confidentiality - the results of the work of a psychologist, which cannot be disclosed without the consent of the person with whom he communicates.

The situation can be discussed in groups (3-4 people each), each of which confirms its solution and outlines approaches to shaping the child's personality. For teachers of the course "Pedagogical Psychology", the recommended seminar topics after each chapter will be useful. Pedagogical psychology is a branch of psychology that studies the facts, laws, and mechanisms of personality formation in the educational process.

There are various interpretations on the topic of educational psychology in the modern psychological and pedagogical literature. On the one hand, pedagogical psychology manifests itself as a limited integrated field of knowledge that occupies a definite place between psychology and pedagogy and has become a field of joint study of the interrelationships between upbringing, education and development of the younger generation. On the other hand, focus on the theory of the gradual formation of mental movements developed by P.Ya. Halperin is defined as a learning process that includes the subject of learning psychology, its structure, characteristics, forms of learning process, age and individual characteristics of the learner, the conditions that give the greatest developmental effect. The object of pedagogical activity is the process of education and upbringing, and the subject is

the approximate part of the students. This definition does not include areas of educational psychology such as educational psychology and teacher labor psychology. A.V. Emphasizing the integral connection between youth and pedagogical psychology, Petrovsky believes that "the subject of pedagogical psychology is the study of the psychological laws of upbringing and education." In his view, pedagogical psychology studies the management of the learning process, the formation of cognitive processes, seeks reliable criteria for mental development, determines the conditions for its achievement, considers the relationship between students. Due to the complexity of the educational process, there is a tendency to emphasize the multifaceted nature of the science of educational psychology, which is based on the facts, mechanisms and patterns of mastering the socio-cultural experience of the individual (child). organization and management of development as a subject of educational activity. educator.

Pedagogical psychology is an evolving field of professional psychological activity aimed at solving current problems of education. Psychological education service began to take shape in 1970 in Russia. Using the modern achievements of pedagogical psychology, it increases the effectiveness of the teaching and educational process. In 1999, the "Regulations on the service of applied psychology in the system of the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation" was developed. This Regulation aims to shape the developing lifestyle of students, develop their creative abilities, create a positive motivation for learning, as well as identify the psychological causes of

personal and social developmental disorders and prevent the occurrence of such disorders as the main goal of the psychological education service. Traditionally, pedagogical psychology as a science is expected to study, explain, and describe phenomena that occur in education. However, teachers and psychologists who are directly involved in educational practice sometimes do not find answers to questions that are very important to them in pedagogical psychology: what are the goals, content and purpose of the teacher and psychologist in modern society, what to do with this or that problem professional situation?

Representatives and practitioners of academic psychology have different subjects of professional activity, goals and means of its implementation, different professional languages. The proposed method of scientific and practical interaction, especially as complex as education, is not effective enough. This is because the recommendations lag behind the rapidly evolving real-life situation in its laws. Also, who uses them is not always taken into account. Practical psychologists also work in a difficult situation.

On the one hand, the results of scientific research enrich their views on the essence of the learning process, on the other hand, they often do not find answers to them, in particular, the following questions: What is the meaning of the work of a practical psychologist in education? How are the activities of a psychologist and a teacher related? How to build the technology of psychological work with the subjects of the learning process? The scientific world has recognized the need to

understand educational psychology as a socio-cultural and practice-changing science. "Science must be viewed in terms of the world of humanity and its inclusion in the processes of human creation in this world."

Today, the methodology, theory, and methodology of teaching, especially educational psychology, has "got rid of the status of the lowest genre, not worthy of scientific consideration, and educational practices that do not affect people but change situations on a regular basis. has become a testing ground for the discovery of new anthropotechnical methods and tools. its interaction with people and with itself. Thus, pedagogical psychology not only studies the psychological mechanisms and laws of the processes occurring in education, but also seeks to integrate them into modern teaching practice. In this regard, the subject of educational psychology is the mechanisms, laws and conditions that ensure the process of personality formation in the learning process. As an applied science, pedagogical psychology focuses on the psychological support of the learning process, which involves identifying and designing effective ways for the psychologist and teacher to work with the teaching practice.

Pedagogical psychology is a field of science that is closely related to age and differential psychology, psycho-genetics, pedagogy, social psychology, philosophy and cultural studies.

The main tasks of educational psychology are:

- to study the mechanisms that provide the necessary conditions for the mental

development and formation of personality of students at each age;

- identification and design of social and pedagogical conditions that contribute to the maximum development of the personal development, self-determination and self-development of the subjects of the educational process;

- Development of methodological tools to identify and predict the characteristics of the intellectual and personal development of the child;

- to study the psychological characteristics of the participants in the learning process (parents, teachers, school administration) and the mechanisms of their impact on the child.

The structure of pedagogical psychology includes three parts: the psychology of pedagogical activity, the psychology of education, and the psychology of education.

Psychology of pedagogical activity studies the structure of the teacher, his personality and communication features, stages and patterns of professional skills. Particular attention is paid to the relationship between teachers, the causes and methods of resolving conflict situations. Recently, the attention of scientists and practitioners has been focused on the development of technologies aimed at ensuring the professional and personal development of teachers, creating optimal conditions for interaction with the leaders of the educational institution.

Educational psychology studies the patterns of the learning process, the peculiarities of the formation of learning activities, its motivational problems, the

peculiarities of the formation of cognitive processes in the classroom, the role of the teacher in developing creative potential and the child's positive self-concept. Within the framework of educational psychology is provided psychological analysis of forms and methods of teaching aimed at ensuring the development of knowledge, skills and psychologically healthy person.

The formation of modern pedagogical psychology is determined by the humanistic ideas of science, aimed at the formation of an independent, vital personality as a unique spiritual upbringing in the conditions of education and upbringing.

The principle of social purpose. The development of educational psychology is determined by the system of social values and assumptions accepted in the education system and in society as a whole, which determine the social expediency of certain actions of theory and practice. Thus, at the present stage, it becomes socially important to create such education systems that help to nurture an independent, autonomous individual who is able to define and implement his own development and further development goals of the society.

The scientific foundations of the concept of modern education are classical and modern, pedagogical and psychological approaches - humanistic, evolving, competency-based, age-dependent, individual, active, person-centered.

Much has been said and written in recent years about the personal direction of teaching. Apparently, no one should believe that students should be paid attention to their personal qualities in the teaching

process. But to what extent has the attitude of teachers towards the planning and conduct of lessons from academic subjects changed in the context of the GEF? Which course technologies are best suited for a private lesson?

Today, Russian education is experiencing a decisive stage in its development. Another attempt at reform in the new millennium is through updating the overall structure and content of education. The key to success in this regard is an in-depth, conceptual, normative and methodological study of the issues of modernization of general education, involving a wide range of scientists, methodologists, education management specialists, teachers, as well as students and their parents. is to do.

The loss of universal values, spirituality, culture has led to the need for a highly developed individual through the development of cognitive interests. And today, the second-generation federal state education standard is aimed at implementing a qualitatively new model of person-centered development of public school, aimed at ensuring the fulfillment of key tasks, including student personality, creative ability, to form an interest in learning, a desire to learn, and an ability.

Personal and individual approaches answer the question of what needs to be developed. The answer to this question can be formulated as follows: it is necessary to identify and develop the individual abilities and inclinations of the student, rather than a single set of qualities that constitute an abstract "graduation model" focused on the

interests of the state. This is ideal, but it is important to remember that education should take into account not only individual abilities and inclinations, but also the social order to produce professionals and citizens. Therefore, it is expedient to formulate the school task as follows: the development of the individual, taking into account the social requirements and the requirements for the development of his qualities, which includes a socially oriented socio-personal, more precisely, cultural-personal model.

According to the person-centered approach, the success of the

implementation of this model is ensured through the development and improvement of the individual mode of action, which is formed on the basis of individual characteristics.

An active approach answers the question of how to develop. Its essence is related to the manifestation and development of skills in activities. In addition, according to the person-centered approach, activities that match a person's abilities and inclinations make a significant contribution to his or her development.

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